

FAIR-IMPACT

Expanding FAIR solutions across EOSC

Project Title	Expanding FAIR solutions across EOSC
Project Acronym	FAIR-IMPACT
Grant Agreement No.	101057344
Start Date of Project	2022-06-01
Duration of Project	36 months
Project Website	https://fair-impact.eu/

D7.2 - FAIR adoption pathway white paper

Work Package	WP7 - Dissemination, exploitation and communication
Lead Author (Org)	Joy Davidson (UEDIN-DCC)
Contributing Author(s) (Org)	Clara Lines (UEDIN-DCC), Marialetizia Mari (Trust-IT) , Elizabeth Newbold (UKRI-STFC), Deborah Thorpe (KNAW-DANS), Maaïke Verburg (KNAW-DANS)
Due Date	2025-04-30
Date	2025-04-17
Version	V1.0 - DRAFT not yet approved by the European Commission
DOI	10.5281/zenodo.15210109

Dissemination Level

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	PU: Public
<input type="checkbox"/>	PP: Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission)
<input type="checkbox"/>	RE: Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission)
<input type="checkbox"/>	CO: Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission)

Funded by
the European Union

Versioning and contribution history

Version	Date	Author	Notes
0.1	2025.XX.XX	Marialetizia Mari (Trust-IT)	TOC
0.2	2025.07.03	Joy Davidson, (UEDIN-DCC)	sections 3, 4 and 5
0.3	2025.19.03	Deborah Thorpe (KNAW-DANS)	additions on mentoring section
0.4	2025.04.01	Joy Davidson (UEDIN-DCC), Maaïke Verburg (KNAW-DANS), Clara Lines (UEDIN-DCC), Elizabeth Newbold (UKRI-STFC)	updated TOC, additions and comments to various sections
0.5	2025.04.04	Joy Davidson (UEDIN-DCC)	draft version submitted to PCO for review
0.6	2025.04.08	Joy Davidson (UEDIN-DCC)	revised version submitted to address comments from reviewers Sandra Boerman, Cecile Guezennec, Vasso Kalaitzi
1.0	2025.04.14	PCO (KNAW-DANS)	Final version published via Zenodo Community

Disclaimer

FAIR-IMPACT has received funding from the European Commission's Horizon Europe funding programme for research and innovation programme under the Grant Agreement no. 101057344. The content of this document does not represent the opinion of the European Commission, and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that might be made of such content.

Table of Contents

Executive Summary	5
1 Introduction & Context	6
2 Summary of FAIR support provided	6
3 Virtual workshops	7
3.1 Highlights	8
3.1.1 Recordings of virtual workshops available as a reference	8
3.1.2 Facilitating exchange fosters a sense of community	8
3.2 Lessons Learned	8
3.2.1 Face to face sessions are still important	8
3.2.2 Too many workshops can be overwhelming	9
3.3 Recommendations	9
4 Peer exchange workshops	9
4.1 Highlights	9
4.1.1 Knowledge exchange	9
4.2 Lessons learned	9
4.2.1 The duration of the peer exchange workshops can impact usefulness	9
4.2.2 Choose the right format for the peer exchange workshops	10
4.2.3 Assign group work during support actions to foster more peer exchange	10
4.3 Recommendations	10
5 Mentoring	10
5.1 Highlights	11
5.1.1 Use of mentoring pairs works well	11
5.1.2 Knowledge exchange and networking	12
5.1.3 There are benefits for mentors	12
5.2 Lessons learned	12
5.2.1 Managing expectations	12
5.2.2 Frequency and scheduling of meetings	12
5.3 Recommendations	13
6 FAIR Implementation stories	13
6.1 Highlights	13
6.1.1 Publication of FAIR Implementation Stories gives credit to authors	13
6.1.2 FAIR Implementation Stories as a trigger point for payment of cascading grants	14
6.2 Lessons learned	14
6.2.1 Large number of stories produced makes it hard to browse	14
6.2.2 Providing a FAIR Implementation Story template made the process more efficient	14
6.3 Recommendations	15
7 Conclusions	15
Annex 1. FAIR-IMPACT's support actions	16
Annex 2. FAIR-IMPACT's support programmes	25

TERMINOLOGY

Terminology/Acronym	Description
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
NLI	National Level Initiatives
RDM	Research data management
Route 1	In kind support programmes
Route 2	Financial support via cascading grants
RPO	Research Performing Organisations
FAIR Implementation Story	A short document that shares the experiences of those supported by FAIR-IMPACT to implement a specific tool or approach.

Executive Summary

Overall, feedback from participants in FAIR-IMPACT's support programmes and support actions has been very positive. FAIR-IMPACT's support offerings focused on one or more of the following aspects:

- delivering virtual workshops
- facilitating peer exchange
- providing access to mentors
- co-producing FAIR implementation stories

This white paper offers a summary of FAIR-IMPACT's support offerings and provides insights into what worked well along with considerations on how the different aspects of support provision could have been made more effective. This paper is intended for support providers from relevant entities, projects and initiatives as they work to develop similar types of support in the future.

1 Introduction & Context

FAIR-IMPACT supported the uptake of FAIR-enabling practices, tools and services among different stakeholder communities at European, national and institutional level, aiming to help realise the vision of a European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) providing access to and reuse of FAIR research outputs. This white paper is intended for support providers from relevant entities, projects and initiatives and provides a summary outlining the practical delivery of FAIR-IMPACT's support offerings while giving insights into what worked well, including lessons learned about how support provision could have been made more effective.

2 Summary of FAIR support provided

To help foster a FAIR ecosystem, FAIR-IMPACT supported three key stakeholder groups - research performing organisations (RPOs), repositories and data services providers, and national level initiatives (NLIs) - to begin or progress their FAIR-enabling journeys. Our aim was to work with research intermediaries rather than directly with individual researchers, aiming to create multipliers and maximise the impact of the support programme. In FAIR-IMPACT, this meant engaging with the organisations who employ researchers, the funding bodies that financially support and influence the way they work, the research support staff who assist them in their day to day work, and the range of infrastructures used to create, share and curate their outputs. FAIR-IMPACT developed three distinct support routes to help these three key stakeholders to become more FAIR-enabling.¹

- **Route 1: in kind support programmes** which provided expert (non-financial) one-to-one support and guidance. Successful applicants to our open calls worked with FAIR-IMPACT mentors to learn how to support the uptake of FAIR-enabling practices. The programme included participation in a series of virtual workshops based on the FAIR Implementation Framework,² carrying out independent homework, and mentoring. These programmes were aimed at those who are just getting started with supporting the FAIR Principles or are less advanced on their FAIR-enabling journey. There were three open calls to join five expert (non-financial) support programmes during the project. For a list of the support programmes provided, please see Annex 2.
- **Route 2: cascading grants** to implement and test specific tools, approaches and methods using financial support. Successful applicants to our open calls received financial support to implement and/or test one or more tools and approaches through a series of virtual, hands-on workshops. For a list of the support actions provided, please see Annex 1. This support was aimed at those who are more

¹ <https://fair-impact.eu/fair-impact-open-calls-support>

² <https://fair-impact.eu/fair-implementation-framework>

advanced on their FAIR-enabling journey and ready to test specific tools and approaches. All those supported through the open calls for financial support were required to prepare a FAIR Implementation Story to provide real-life experiences and lessons learned. There were three open calls for participation in one or more of eleven defined support actions over the life of the FAIR-IMPACT project.

- **Route 3: FAIR Implementation Workshops³** aimed to help our key stakeholders in Europe and globally to become more familiar with FAIR-enabling tools, approaches, and methods. The workshops were free to attend and open to all. We delivered more than 30 FAIR implementation workshops and webinars over the life of the project. The recordings of these events will be openly available beyond the life of the project.

FAIR-IMPACT's support programmes and actions included one or more of the following key aspects:

- delivering **virtual workshops**
- facilitating **peer exchange**
- provision of **mentoring**
- co-production of **FAIR implementation stories**

Overall, the feedback we received from the participants of the support programmes and support actions was very positive and suggests that our approach to delivering support was largely effective. We had a very good response rate for each of the open calls - in most cases well exceeding the number of places we could support through the cascading grants. This response suggests that the kind of support we offered is needed by the community. In the sections below, we will focus on each of the four aspects of the FAIR-IMPACT support programmes and actions and share what worked well, what could have been done differently and provide some recommendations for other providers to consider when developing similar types of support in the future.

3 Virtual workshops

The delivery of virtual workshops were central to all three Routes of support delivery. For the five expert (non-financial) support programmes, participants took part in a minimum of 7 and up to 10 thematic and peer exchange workshops during the support programmes. For participants in the eleven financial support actions, participants joined at least 3 and up to 6 virtual workshops which introduced the tool(s) and/or approach to be implemented and to allow for peer exchange. We also provided 33 public FAIR Implementation Workshops⁴ and a number of webinars relating to the open calls.

³ <https://fair-impact.eu/events/fair-implementation-workshops>

⁴ <https://fair-impact.eu/events/fair-implementation-workshops>

3.1 Highlights

The main reason for employing a purely virtual approach with FAIR-IMPACT's support workshops was to reduce barriers to participation. In addition to being better for the environment, eliminating the need for travel meant that FAIR-IMPACT support providers, external experts and participants were better able to fit in the workshops around their regular work schedules. Below, we provide insights into what worked well with the virtual workshop approach adopted by the FAIR-IMPACT project.

3.1.1 Recordings of virtual workshops available as a reference

By employing a virtual approach to delivering the workshops, we were also able to record the workshops to allow those who may have been unable to attend live the chance to catch up in their own time. These recordings can also serve as a useful resource for others to use beyond those involved in the support programmes and actions and also beyond the life of the FAIR-IMPACT project to support implementation of specific tools and approaches. Work is underway to edit the recordings to share via the support programmes and support action pages.

3.1.2 Facilitating exchange fosters a sense of community

Time was set aside in the majority of the virtual workshops in the RPO support programme to allow the participating teams to work together to start working on homework. This was facilitated through the use of dedicated Zoom breakout rooms for the 20 participating RPOs of which the majority had brought in up to five additional team members from across their organisation. Some participants mentioned that they really valued this approach as it was often difficult to find time to schedule meetings together outside of the workshops. A few of the participating RPOs had only one member in their team in some cases due to the fact that there were no other RDM-related staff in place at their organisation. We encouraged those individuals joining the support programme without a team to consider working together. For some, this approach provided a sense of being part of an RDM community that was lacking at their organisation.

3.2 Lessons Learned

While the approach of providing purely virtual workshops was largely successful and more inclusive, there are some things we might consider doing differently in the future based on our experience.

3.2.1 Face to face sessions are still important

A purely virtual approach to delivering workshops was chosen as it offers many benefits, however it can be challenging to realise effective engagement using this approach alone. Some participants mentioned that they would have liked the opportunity to have at least one face-to-face meeting with their peers. Our FAIRfest event provided one such

opportunity for those who took part in support programmes to meet face to face and engage with the wider community.

3.2.2 Too many workshops can be overwhelming

By going with a virtual approach, we were able to provide a greater number of workshops over a much longer period of time than would have been possible in a face to face programme. However, the number of workshops was a bit overwhelming for some participants.

3.3 Recommendations

When delivering workshops to support the uptake of FAIR-enabling tools and approaches and to help foster a community of practice, employing a mixed approach of both virtual and face-to-face sessions is recommended. Avoid the temptation to cram too many workshops into support programmes.

4 Peer exchange workshops

For both the expert (non-financial) support programmes and the financial support actions we wanted to ensure that participants had the opportunity to share knowledge with each other as well as benefiting from guidance and advice from the support providers. To support knowledge exchange, we included at least one peer exchange workshop as a central component to each of our support programmes and actions.

4.1 Highlights

Below, we share some of the things that worked well with the peer exchange workshops and things that could have been improved.

4.1.1 Knowledge exchange

Participants valued the peer exchange workshops as a way to learn from each other and to extend their professional networks.

4.2 Lessons learned

As noted above, it is challenging to effectively facilitate peer exchange through purely virtual workshops. Below, we share some of the lessons learned through delivering the peer exchange workshops.

4.2.1 The duration of the peer exchange workshops can impact usefulness

Feedback gathered from participants of the first round of the financial support actions indicated that, while the virtual peer exchange workshops offered useful insights, the format

of having each participating team present back-to-back during the peer exchange workshop was quite dense. Participants also felt that the three hour long peer exchange workshops were longer than desired. As the support actions had up to 20 participating teams to present, the format could also become a bit tedious for the participants. Another approach we employed was to cluster the peer exchange workshop agendas around specific themes so that participants could decide which parts of the workshop were of most value to them to join. This approach was generally well received however, if presentations and discussions on one theme ran over time, it could impact negatively on the remaining themes to be explored.

4.2.2 Choose the right format for the peer exchange workshops

Keeping large cohorts in plenary for peer exchange poses some challenges. To make the workshops more useful, different formats were explored in the support programmes and actions with varying success. For example, in one of the support actions the participants of the peer exchange workshop were allocated to one of three parallel breakout groups rather than running the peer exchange session in plenary. This approach allowed much more time for group discussion and exchange, but the downside to this approach is that participants only got to hear from the peers in their breakout group. The support action participants are able to read each others' published FAIR Implementation Stories but distilling the key information in each can require some effort depending on the number of participants in the support action.

4.2.3 Assign group work during support actions to foster more peer exchange

One suggestion that we received via feedback was to consider grouping participating teams to work together on a homework assignment. While we were not able to take this suggestion on board due to time constraints, we do agree that it is a good approach to consider for future support programmes.

4.3 Recommendations

Effective peer exchange needs time to develop and thrive. Carefully consider the cohort of participants you are working with and their interests and levels of maturity with the FAIR principles to help structure the peer exchange workshops to maximise benefits and to facilitate group working in between the workshops.

5 Mentoring

Mentoring was a key aspect of the expert (non-financial) support programmes and was the key mechanism used to provide dedicated, one-to-one support (see Annex 2 for a list of the support programmes offered). Different approaches were employed for the provision of mentoring in the three support programmes.

For our RPO support programme, mentors and mentees held an hour-long meeting once a month once after the participants had chosen a particular thematic area to focus on, after the first six thematic workshops had been delivered. Mentors then helped mentees to define their FAIR implementation action plans and provide support during the actual implementation.

In the first running of the Repositories and Data Service Providers support programme, mentors met with mentees every two weeks from the very start of the support programme to help them draft and implement their action plans. This changed to a monthly frequency during the second running of the support programme as feedback from participants and mentors indicated the biweekly frequency was too high.

In the National Level Initiatives (NLI) support programme there were three mentor meetings held with each of the four participants during the first running of the programme. The second running of the programme had far more participants with multiple participants from many countries. For the second running, a different approach was taken whereby two meetings were set up to enable group discussions with peers from key organisations from each of the participating countries facilitated by two members of the FAIR-IMPACT team.

Our financial support action providers did not provide mentorship as such but rather offered practical advice and guidance to all participants collectively during the series of virtual workshops. The support providers also responded to questions in between the workshops via virtual drop-in sessions, set contact hours, use of slack and/or through the dedicated email lists.

5.1 Highlights

While there were slight variations in the approaches to mentoring provision in the in-kind support programmes, we ensured an overall consistency in the provision of the one-to-one support. We did so by creating mentor checklists which provided step-by-step instructions and advice on what should be covered during the meetings. We also provided links to relevant background documents to review ahead of the meetings.⁵ Below, we share some of the things that worked well with our mentoring provision.

5.1.1 Use of mentoring pairs works well

For the five expert (non-financial) support programmes, we partnered successful applicants to the open calls with two FAIR-IMPACT mentors. We aimed to match mentees with FAIR-IMPACT mentors from the same country, domain or with practical experience in a specific FAIR-enabling area (e.g., developing training, policies). The two-to-one approach ensured that we could provide a broader range of real life experiences from FAIR-IMPACT mentors. In a practical sense, the approach of having two FAIR-IMPACT mentors per participating team reduced the risk that a team may lose their one-to-one support in the event of illness, staff turnover and during the holiday period.

⁵ RPO Support Programme Mentor's Checklist
<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1fGJoy32VjxYVagKDbZZXk0rOrHTOwXSV/view?usp=sharing>

5.1.2 Knowledge exchange and networking

The mentors represented a wide variety of backgrounds, expertise areas and domain specialisms relating to FAIR and research data management. Mentors in the project had access to a wider network of experts and links with other INFRAEOSC projects⁶ which provided participants with opportunities for networking and access to additional expertise.

5.1.3 There are benefits for mentors

It is important to note that the mentors also had the opportunity to exchange information and gain knowledge from the mentees, as it was very much a two way conversation. Many of the mentors found that working as part of a mentor pair was beneficial for professional development and offered an opportunity for networking. As there were multiple expert (non-financial) support programmes running at the same time, each FAIR-IMPACT mentor ended up working collaboratively with a range of other FAIR-IMPACT mentors to deliver the support. This provided a useful opportunity to learn from each other and to experience different approaches to mentoring, collaborating, and working in general, and provide useful networking opportunities while maximising impact.

5.2 Lessons learned

While the mentoring approach had many positive aspects, there were some things that could have been done differently. We share some of the lessons learned below.

5.2.1 Managing expectations

Some participants in the first round of the financial support actions said that they expected to receive more on demand and one-to-one support from the providers during the support action. A key message to us was to make even more clear in the support action descriptions the types and amount of expert support that could be expected.

5.2.2 Frequency and scheduling of meetings

Two FAIR-IMPACT mentors worked with each of the participating teams across the five expert (non-financial) support programmes which ran in parallel between early 2024 and early 2025. Successful applicants to the support programmes were encouraged to bring in up to four additional team members to participate in the support programmes. Given the number of mentors and mentees that might be involved in each meeting, scheduling could be quite difficult. This was especially true during the summer holiday period. It was also difficult to get the frequency of meetings right. If meetings between mentors and mentees were too frequent, there was often not enough progress to report while if the meetings were too infrequent, it was difficult to keep momentum going. It is important to mutually

⁶ Projects funded under the Horizon Europe Research Infrastructures programme in order to contribute to the implementation of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).

agree on a frequency of meetings that is appropriate for the work being carried out and to reflect the context in which the work is happening.

5.3 Recommendations

It is important to provide clarity on what mentors can be expected to provide and to manage mentees' expectations. Provide guidance and instructions to mentors to ensure that there is consistency in the approach together with a standard level of quality. Checklists and guidance documents can help with this. If resources allow, provision of training for mentors is also advisable.

The frequency of meetings between mentors and mentees depends to a large extent on the specific individuals involved. Wherever possible, provide some flexibility in your overall approach to meet individual preferences.

6 FAIR Implementation stories

FAIR-IMPACT adapted the FAIR Implementation Story template that was developed in FAIRsFAIR and made available under a CC Attribution 4.0 licence.⁷ FAIR Implementation Stories aim to share real life examples of approaches to implementing the FAIR principles and to provide useful insights that will help others considering the adoption of similar approaches. The stories are intentionally short (only 2-4 pages long in general) to reduce barriers to their reuse and to ensure that key messages can be conveyed concisely. All those supported through financial support were obliged to prepare a FAIR Implementation Story as a condition of award. Participants of the expert (non-financial) support programmes were also invited to prepare FAIR Implementation Stories but it was not mandatory.

6.1 Highlights

Below we share some of the things that worked well with the creation and publication of FAIR Implementation Stories.

6.1.1 Publication of FAIR Implementation Stories shares knowledge and gives credit to authors

The FAIR implementation stories are published to our Zenodo community⁸ and are assigned with persistent identifiers (PIDs). This helps to share the lessons learned during the support sections more widely and gives the participants a citable output linked to the work they carried out.

⁷ <https://www.fairsfair.eu/implementation-adoption-stories>

⁸ <https://zenodo.org/communities/fair-impact/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

6.1.2 FAIR Implementation Stories provide a trigger point for issuing payment of cascading grants

All those supported financially through the cascading grants had to prepare an individual FAIR Implementation Story as a condition of grant. The submission of the draft story proved to be a useful way to provide evidence that the expected work was carried out during the support action and provided a trigger point for the cascading grant funds to be paid to the participant.

6.2 Lessons learned

We share some of the lessons learned in the development and publication of our collection of FAIR Implementation Stories below.

6.2.1 Large number of stories produced makes it hard to browse

We delivered eleven support actions and each action had between 8-20 participants meaning that we ended up with a very large number of FAIR Implementation stories on our website.⁹ The sheer volume of stories makes it difficult to browse the contents to find information that is potentially useful. To make the stories easier to navigate, a number of tags were implemented to help end users to browse the content and to find the most appropriate stories for their specific needs (e.g., by tool, by stakeholder type, by topic). We also linked the stories to the relevant tools in the FAIR Implementation Catalogue of Resources¹⁰ so that users of the catalogue might discover the Implementation stories through a different route.

6.2.2 Providing a FAIR Implementation Story template made the process more efficient

During the first round of support actions¹¹ FAIR Implementation stories were co-developed based on notes taken during a mandatory exit interview. This approach was continued in both runnings of the Repository Support Programmes and the first running of the National Level Initiatives Support Programme.¹² However, for the RPO Support Programme¹³ and the second¹⁴ and third¹⁵ round of funded support actions, this approach became difficult to sustain due to the numbers involved in each support programme and action. To better enable the timely drafting of the implementation stories, templates were developed and shared with participants to complete independently. The drafts were reviewed by the FAIR-IMPACT team prior to publishing in our Zenodo community. The quality of the stories

⁹ <https://fair-impact.eu/implementation-adoption-stories>

¹⁰ <https://catalogue.fair-impact.eu/>

¹¹ <https://fair-impact.eu/1st-open-call-route-2-support-closed>

¹² <https://fair-impact.eu/apply-non-financial-support>

¹³ <https://fair-impact.eu/2nd-open-call-support-opens-30-august>

¹⁴ <https://fair-impact.eu/2nd-open-call-route-2-support>

¹⁵ <https://fair-impact.eu/3rd-open-cal-route-2-support-opens-30-sept>

produced in this way has been excellent and the amended approach meant that participants could complete the story on their own time scale rather than waiting for an exit interview to be scheduled and carried out. In addition, asking for completion of the draft story in a very short timeframe of 10 days after the completion of the support action seemed to work better than offering a longer time frame of around 30 days - possibly because the information is still fresh in the participants' mind.

6.3 Recommendations

We believe that there is value in contributing to the body of FAIR Implementation Stories going forward. However, we recommend exploring the approach of all participants of a given support action working together as joint authors of a single story which will potentially avoid any duplication of information and, more importantly, make it easier to indicate any country or discipline specific views on a particular approach or tool in a single output. The review and publishing of the stories has been quite arduous based on the sheer number that were produced. By developing only one joint story per support action rather than one story per participant the burden of review and publication will also be reduced. By having participants work together on a single FAIR Implementation Story as co-authors rather than in isolation, we can also foster additional knowledge exchange while still ensuring that each participant has a citable output relating to their work.

If adopting the FAIR Implementation Story approach, take the time to consider how you will facilitate access to the stories to improve their findability. Clustering and labelling the stories with tags helps. Distilling the common themes from a set of stories can also be helpful.

7 Conclusions

Overall, the feedback we received from the participants of the support programmes and support actions was very positive and suggests that our approach to delivering support was largely effective and that such support is needed. However, there were things that would have improved the overall experience and effectiveness of the support provision. We hope that the insights that we have shared in this white paper helps other support providers to make their offerings more effective as they work to develop similar types of support in the future.

Annex 1. FAIR-IMPACT’s support actions

In the table below, we provide a list of the support actions that were offered during the three open calls for Route 2 cascading grants over the three years of the FAIR-IMPACT project.

<p>FAIRness assessment challenge¹⁶</p>	<p>More harmonised use of semantic artefacts such as ontologies, terminologies, taxonomies, thesauri, vocabularies, metadata schemas and standards is a key element to achieving a high level of FAIRness. However, it can often be difficult to find and use semantic artefacts as they themselves are not always FAIR. Building on the successful “FAIRness hackathon approach” that was used by the French agri-food project FooSIN as well as on the FAIRsFAIR iterative FAIR pilot assessment and consultation experience, this targeted support action will help a cohort of dataset providers or semantic artefact developers to self-assess the level of FAIRness of their resources (datasets, semantic artefacts, or any collections of those) with several FAIRness assessment tools and methods put at their disposal by FAIR-IMPACT. The cohort participated in a month-long joint challenge during which they will apply a variety of assessment tools including F-UJI, O’FAIRE and FOOPS, and methods such as the FAIR Data Maturity Model (FDMM) and the Ten simple rules for FAIR vocabularies to self-assess their resource(s). The objective for all participants was to maximise the FAIRness of their own resources as expressed by the scores obtained using the various tools used during the span of the challenge.</p> <p>Based on their FAIRness score at the beginning of the challenge, participants developed a plan to implement changes to improve those scores and their effort will be measured with the new score obtained at the end of the challenge period.</p> <p>During the support action, FAIR-IMPACT mentors provided guidance and tips on how to improve their score by providing support either directly on the tools methodology available or with general FAIR-enabling feedback and advice.</p>
---	---

¹⁶ <https://fair-impact.eu/support-offer-1-fairness-assessment-challenge-datasets-and-semantic-artefacts>

Signposting and RO-Crate¹⁷

The findability of a wide range of research objects and their related metadata are central to the FAIR principles. This support action combined two successful approaches (FAIR Signposting and RO-Crate) to help ensure that research objects can be packaged up with structured metadata to support reuse and that these packages can be exposed for improved findability.

FAIR Signposting is a method to expose machine-actionable navigation links that indicate downloadable resources, types and attribution – particularly for scholarly and institutional repositories which use persistent identifiers like DOIs. Signposting makes explicit the links between a typical HTML landing page and the downloadable resources that are available for the research object described by that landing pages, including content resources and machine-readable metadata such as in RDF, although the method is technology-agnostic in terms of metadata formats. It also links to persistent identifiers, both for the research object and its authors. Signposting uses existing standards to achieve this. Repositories currently implementing Signposting include Dataverse and WorkflowHub.

RO-Crate has been established as a community effort to practically achieve FAIR packaging of research objects (digital objects like data, methods, software, etc.) with their structured metadata. RO-Crate is based on well-established Web standards and FAIR principles. For its common metadata representations, RO-Crate builds on schema.org, a mature and general mark-up vocabulary used by search engines including Google Dataset Search. RO-Crate libraries are available for Javascript, Python, Ruby and Java, and in addition any RDF tooling supporting JSON-LD can be used (e.g. for knowledge graphs). RO-Crate is being adopted by a range of EU/EOSC projects and can be seen as a pragmatic implementation of the FAIR digital objects vision as highlighted by EOSC's Interoperability Framework.

During the support action, participants worked to develop their implementation ideas with support from the FAIR-IMPACT support providers. Participants were not

¹⁷<https://fair-impact.eu/support-offer-2-enabling-fair-signposting-and-ro-crate-contentmetadata-discovery-and-consumption>

	<p>competing during the support action but rather encouraged to collaborate using a dedicated Slack server, to foster cross-implementation integration.</p>
<p>Assessment and improvement of existing research software using a new extension of F-UJI¹⁸</p>	<p>Research software is an essential component of academic research, both as a tool and an outcome or result of the research process. While the importance of findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable (FAIR) research data for Open Science is well recognised, guidelines and best practices for research software development and curation are less well established.</p> <p>Modeled on the FAIR data principles, the FAIR principles for research software (FAIR4RS Principles) aims to guide software creators and owners in how to make their software FAIR. Specifically, FAIR research software needs to be well-described by metadata, inspectable, documented, and appropriately structured so that it can be executed, replicated, built-upon, combined, and used in different settings.</p> <p>To enhance the FAIRness and impact of research software, FAIR-IMPACT offered two support programmes aimed at software developers in different disciplines. One of these support programmes, Assessment and Improvement of Research Software, involved piloting a new F-UJI extension for automated FAIR software assessment and improvement.</p>
<p>Implementing the Research Software MetaData guidelines¹⁹</p>	<p>Research software plays a crucial role in scientific research, both as a tool and a final product. Modeled on the FAIR data principles, the FAIR principles for research software (FAIR4RS Principles) aim to guide software creators and owners in how to make their software findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable (FAIR). Building on that foundation, the Research Software MetaData (RSMD) Guidelines provide a comprehensive and flexible set of metadata recommendations that can be applied across different disciplines and different software development contexts.</p>

¹⁸ <https://fair-impact.eu/support-offer-1-assessment-and-improvement-research-software>

¹⁹ <https://fair-impact.eu/support-offer-1-assessment-and-improvement-research-software>

	<p>To promote the adoption of the FAIR4RS Principles and the RSDM Guidelines, and enhance the FAIRness of research software, FAIR-IMPACT offered two support programmes aimed at software developers in different disciplines. The second of these support programmes focused on Implementing the Research Software MetaData (RSMD) Guidelines for better describing, citing, referencing, and archiving research software artefacts.</p>
<p>Creating EOSC compliant Persistent Identifier (PID) policies²⁰</p>	<p>The persistent identification of research outputs is part of good research data management practice and is central to the FAIR Principles and the vision of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). There are many types of persistent identifiers (PIDs) currently being used to identify data and other kinds of research outputs but also different actors involved in the creation of outputs and the organisations that employ them or fund their work. To foster harmonisation on the use of different persistent identifiers, there is a need to define and implement research data and/or PID policies. A PID policy for the EOSC was approved in 2020 and defines a set of expectations about what persistent identifiers will be used within the context of EOSC to support a functioning environment of FAIR research as well as requirements of PID providers and the basic services they offer.</p> <p>In this support action, successful applicants carried out self-assessments with regard to PID policy readiness using the EOSC PID Policy as a guide. This was made possible through the beta version of the FAIRCORE4EOSC Compliance Assessment Toolkit (CAT) service, which strives to encode, record, and query compliance with the EOSC PID policy and more (including TRUST, FAIR, Reproducibility, GDPR, and Licences). To enable participation across a range of PID providers, this support action did not focus on any specific PID type but rather provide general best practice guidelines on the creation and assessment of PID policies.</p>

²⁰ <https://fair-impact.eu/support-offer-5-cat-and-pid-policies>

<p>Recommendations for trustworthy and FAIR-enabling data repositories²¹</p>	<p>Transparent assessment and clear communication of repository trustworthiness help build confidence in digital repositories and support the FAIRness of their content. To support this goal, FAIR-IMPACT has been developing guidelines to help repositories expose relevant metadata at both the organisational and object levels. Implementing these guidelines enhances discovery, provides essential context, and fosters interoperability, ultimately strengthening trust in repositories and the digital objects they manage.</p> <p>This support action provided participants with an opportunity to engage with these evolving guidelines, critically assess their applicability, and contribute to their refinement. By analysing the guidelines in the context of their own repositories, participants identified ways to improve the transparency of their services while shaping the next iteration of the guidelines. Key aspects of the guidelines included exposing metadata related to repository characteristics (e.g., identifiers, contact details, and business models), indicators of trustworthiness (e.g., standards followed, preservation policies, and certifications), and FAIRness-related information (e.g., assessment results and tools used).</p> <p>Over the course of the support action, participants received expert guidance to evaluate and enhance how their repositories communicate trustworthiness and FAIRness. They also provided direct feedback on the relevance, clarity, and feasibility of the guidelines. Their insights will inform the next phase of this work, which will focus on practical implementation through a prototype.</p>
<p>Improving the availability and machine readability of data policies with FAIRsharing²²</p>	<p>In recent years policymakers at the national, funding body, publisher, and organisational levels have been working to ensure that their policies support the creation and reuse of data that are findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR). Monitoring progress across the changing policy landscape is labour intensive and largely achieved</p>

²¹ <https://fair-impact.eu/support-offer-6-recommendations-trustworthy-and-fair-enabling-data-repositories>

²² <https://fair-impact.eu/support-offer-7-improving-availability-and-machine-readability-data-policies-fairsharing>

	<p>through the completion of annual surveys and/or desk research. In addition, monitoring tends to focus on the existence of such policies rather than on their content and often looks only at what is happening at the national and funding body levels meaning that organisational level policies are often not taken into account.</p> <p>The FAIRsFAIR project released their FAIR-enabling data policy checklist in 2022 to help policy makers self-assess whether elements of existing data policies are FAIR-enabling as well as providing recommendations on what should be addressed when developing new data policies. The checklist was also intended to help harmonise the description of policy content to improve its comparability and, to this end, a structured policy description template was created based on the content of the checklist. FAIRsharing - a curated, informative and educational resource on data and metadata standards, databases and policies - updated their own policy metadata in 2023 to reflect the fields covered by the FAIRsFAIR policy checklist and template. As a result, policies registered with FAIRsharing can now make the content of their policies more explicit and comparable by both humans and machines which could make monitoring the policy landscape more straightforward and efficient in the years to come.</p> <p>This support action worked with individuals/small teams to support them to coordinate the registration of data policies from stakeholders in their country/region/domain with the FAIRsharing registry and consider how we can leverage this shared pool of information for ongoing policy monitoring activities. Successful applicants received 4000 € to support their participation which required about 8 days of effort from participants between May-September 2024.</p> <p>Participants of the support action were supported in coordinating the registration of data policies in FAIRsharing, and worked collectively to consider how the registered policy data could be leveraged for ongoing monitoring of the policy landscape. This increased the availability of data policies within their country/region/domain.</p>
--	---

<p>Managing data types, schemas and vocabularies and crosswalks for FAIR researcher related metadata²³</p>	<p>The support action will introduce successful applicants to three tools developed by the FAIRCORE4EOSC (FC4E) project. These included:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data Type Registry (DTR) which allows for machine-actionable standardisation and enrichment of metadata schema elements and other relevant types of data • Vocabulary service which allows for the creation, curation and distribution of controlled vocabularies for any purpose, simple or complex. • Metadata Schema and Crosswalk Registry (MSCR) which supports interoperability between resource catalogues and information systems using different (metadata) schemas and encourage organisations and especially researchers to share their metadata interoperability work by registering and publishing the metadata crosswalks used in their workflows that are currently not visible (FAIRification)". Provides an alternative for project specific schema/data type and crosswalk specifications. <p>In this support action the participants used one or more of the FC4E tools to enhance the machine-actionability of their existing schema and crosswalk specifications. This could mean for example the registration of schema from public APIs to the MSCR and creation of mappings from those service specific data models to common formats such as Datacite and DCAT or creating a metadata schema using enriched schema elements registered in the DTR.</p>
<p>Creating EOSC compliant interoperability policies based on EOSC Interoperability Framework (IF)²⁴</p>	<p>One of the main concerns when we deploy a service, especially those related to data, is how this service can work with others. This is relevant for services to be integrated in the EOSC ecosystem. The creation of the EOSC Interoperability Framework is an effort to analyse the gaps and problems addressed in this context. Also, it provides recommendations to improve this integration.</p>

²³ <https://fair-impact.eu/managing-data-schemas-vocabularies>

²⁴ <https://fair-impact.eu/creating-eosc-compliant-interoperability-policies>

	<p>One of the challenges is to translate these recommendations into specific actions. This question is addressed in the work being done by FAIR IMPACT in the context of the production of interoperability guidelines. In this support action, selected participants analysed the interoperability status of their services using the FAIRCORE4EOSC Compliance Assessment Tool (CAT). After this analysis, participants identified actions that they could then carry out to improve the interoperability of their services based on the guidelines and support provided.</p>
<p>Testing the trustworthy and FAIR-enabling repositories prototype²⁵</p>	<p>FAIR-enabling and trustworthy data repositories play a central role in making and keeping data FAIR over time. While there is ongoing debate on what constitutes trustworthiness, there is broad agreement that transparency and evidence is essential to enable end users to make informed decisions about the repository services they use.</p> <p>In this support action successful applicants will have the opportunity to test a prototype developed by FAIR-IMPACT to expose relevant metadata at the organisational and object level. Participants will also have the opportunity to learn about these updated Guidelines for repositories and registries on exposing repository trustworthiness status and FAIR data assessments outcomes. The focus of this support action is on digital data repositories with access to the hosting infrastructure and technical expertise. Specifically repositories which are interested in increasing the findability and interoperability of their organisation by exposing machine actionable metadata about themselves and their datasets.</p>
<p>Implementation of a shared API for semantic catalogues²⁶</p>	<p>This support action invited Semantic Artefact Catalogue (SAC) providers to apply to implement an API based on the Metadata for Ontology Description and Publication (MOD) ontology to promote interoperability and enhance access to SACs. This API enables a uniform interface to semantic artefacts (SA), enabling seamless querying by stakeholders, regardless of domain. This open call was an opportunity for</p>

²⁵ <https://fair-impact.eu/testing-tdr-and-fair-enabling-prototype>

²⁶ <https://fair-impact.eu/implementing-shared-api-for-semantic-catalogues>

	<p>SACs to participate in a community-driven effort to improve the FAIRness of their resources through the adoption of this API.</p> <p>As part of the work of WP4 on Metadata and Ontologies FAIR-IMPACT has established a draft specification of a candidate shared/standard API for SACs. The first version of this draft API is described in D4.3 Specification of shared metadata description of semantic artefacts and their catalogues including common reference API. In this specification, the Metadata for Ontology Description and Publication (MOD) ontology, provides a reference vocabulary to semantically describe SAs and their catalogues, including the list of objects (extended from DCAT2) and their properties. MOD is itself the subject of another deliverable, M4.3 Specification of semantic artefact description. The MOD-API for SACs is designed to provide unified access to the catalogue content (i.e., the artefacts, their distribution and their records), enabling seamless querying and use by stakeholders independent of domain. The MOD-API is formalised by means of an OpenAPI template designed to guide the implementation of Web REST APIs.</p> <p>This support offer was a call for implementations of the MOD-API by existing SACs. FAIR-IMPACT is offering support to relevant labs, institutions or infrastructure already providing (some kind of) SAC and who are willing to implement the MOD-API on top of their catalogues to ease the use of their services and enable a better interoperability between all SACs.</p>
--	---

Annex 2. FAIR-IMPACT’s support programmes

In the table below, we provide a list of the support programmes that were offered during the three open calls for Route 1 support over the three years of the FAIR-IMPACT project.

<p>Support programme for National Level Initiatives²⁷</p>	<p>Participation in this nine month long support programme aimed to help national organisations and researchers to better understand the drivers for becoming more FAIR-enabling, to assess their current FAIR-enabling capabilities and develop plans for improvement, and to ensure that they have an effective engagement strategy in place to facilitate uptake at the national level.</p> <p>This support program was open to all but especially dedicated to organisations working at a national level and researchers to build adoption of FAIR practices. National initiatives and mandated organisations are both targets and providers of the webinars.</p> <p>The support programme began in January 2024 as a series of eight virtual workshops where participants were introduced to key concepts that can support their journey toward becoming FAIR-enabling. As part of the programme, participants carried out a supported self-assessment of their current capabilities and developed action plans to improve one or more areas. Participants received one-to-one support from FAIR-IMPACT over a period of nine months as they implemented their action plans. A series of curated webinars showcased specific tools and approaches to provide inspiration on how to implement FAIR in a practical sense. These webinars were open to the public as well as to participants of the support programme.</p> <p>Enabling knowledge exchange was a key objective of the support programme and two peer exchange workshops were held in month six and month nine to allow the 4 participating teams to share their experiences.</p>
<p>Support programme for Research Performing Organisations²⁸</p>	<p>Participation in this nine month long support programme helped research performing organisations to better understand the drivers for becoming more FAIR-enabling, to assess their current FAIR-enabling capacity and develop plans for improvement, and to ensure that they have an effective engagement strategy in place to facilitate uptake across the organisation. The structure of the programme is based around the FAIR Implementation Framework stages.</p> <p>The support programme began in February 2024 as a series of</p>

²⁷ <https://fair-impact.eu/2nd-open-call-support-opens-30-august>

²⁸ *ibid*

	<p>ten virtual workshops where participants were introduced to key concepts that can support their journey toward becoming more FAIR-enabling. As part of the programme, participants carried out a supported self-assessment of their current capabilities and to develop action plans to improve one or more areas.</p> <p>The 20 successful applicants to this support programme received:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • a review of their research data policy and recommendations from their FAIR-IMPACT mentors on how to make it more FAIR-enabling. If they do not yet have a research data policy, support will be provided from FAIR-IMPACT mentors to start developing one. • support from their mentors to plan and deliver one local workshop bringing together different stakeholders across their organisation to self-assess current FAIR-enabling capabilities. • one-to-one support from FAIR-IMPACT mentors to develop their actions plans and define their engagement strategies.
<p>Repositories and Data service Providers Support Programme²⁹</p>	<p>The FAIR Principles focus on characteristics of digital objects that make them Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable. Achieving and maintaining those characteristics depends on the individuals and organisations that create, store, curate, and preserve the objects. These activities are 'FAIR-enabling', and repositories and data service providers play an important role in facilitating them.</p> <p>The nine month long support programme with 6 participating teams began in January 2024 as a series of virtual workshops where we introduced key concepts around FAIR and how they may apply to organisations. A series of curated webinars showcased specific tools and approaches that could help participants to implement the FAIR principles in a practical sense and participants had the opportunity to do some virtual 'sight-seeing' at some of our partners' organisations to see how they implement certain FAIR-enabling practices.</p> <p>Participants received one-to-one support from the FAIR-IMPACT support team over a period of nine months as they developed and implemented their action plans. Enabling knowledge exchange was one of the key objectives of the support programme. To this end, two workshops were held in June and September where participants shared their experiences with peers in the support programme. The programme wrapped-up with a personal exit interview that resulted in a co-produced 'FAIR Implementation Story' which we published in our Zenodo community to share the unique experience of each participant and enable networking with the wider community.</p>

²⁹ <https://fair-impact.eu/2nd-open-call-support-opens-30-august>

<p>Second running of the support programme for national-level initiatives³⁰</p>	<p>A second running of the programme for national-level initiatives ran between September 2024 and January 2025. Through this programme, participants had the opportunity to engage with experts in a series of virtual workshops covering a range of topics, including training, funding, convincing decision-makers, engaging researchers, and showcasing national initiatives. These sessions aimed to provide comprehensive insights into what is achievable at the national level for FAIR.</p>
<p>Second running of the support programme for Repositories and Data Service Providers³¹</p>	<p>Between September 2024 and March 2025, nine participating teams received one-to-one support from the FAIR-IMPACT support team over a period of nine months as they developed and implemented their action plans.</p>

³⁰ <https://fair-impact.eu/second-call-national-level-initiatives>

³¹ <https://fair-impact.eu/2nd-open-call-route-1-expert-non-financial-support-open>